

DEVELOPING PRAGMATIC COMPETENCE WITH ENGLISH SCHOOL TEXTBOOKS

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Abstract: The paper focuses on the importance of pragmatic competence acquisition in the EFL classroom and on the great role the textbook plays in this process. It provides the results of an analysis of five English textbooks used in the schools of Moldova in the first five years of pupils' studying English. The results show that all the textbooks contain some implicit and explicit pragmatic information, which, however, is not equally distributed. Special attention was paid to the treatment of speech acts in the textbooks. The results show that the success of pragmatic competence development depends on several factors revealed in the paper.

Keywords: pragmatic competence, pragmatic information, speech acts, metalanguage, pronominal reference, politeness, communication failure.

Since the adoption of the communicative approach, the aim of foreign language teaching in our schools has been to prepare students for communication, i.e. more attention has been paid to developing students' abilities to understand and produce language in conformity with the situations of speech. In spite of this, teachers continued to focus on developing students' linguistic competence, one of the reasons in Moldova being the structure and content of the Bacalaureate exam that students pass after twelve years of school education. It is an important exam which, however, excludes the possibility to assess students' ability to communicate and does not measure the students' pragmatic competence. This has led to the underestimation of the necessity to teach language in use. Meanwhile linguists have focused

on the importance of pragmatic knowledge in becoming proficient in a foreign language finding that often very good knowledge of grammar and vocabulary does not mean that learners become proficient speakers. They emphasize the necessity of teaching pragmatics to develop students' pragmatic competence because lack of this competence is often the reason why communication fails. The authors of numerous recent works (Blum-Kulka, Kasper, Leech, Ogiermann, Vellinga, etc) devoted to developing pragmatic competence in EFL, have opposed the traditional approach towards foreign language teaching that ignores the necessity to teach learners how to use the language and to develop their pragmatic competence by highlighting the crucial role of the latter in successful foreign language acquisition. More and more linguists have emphasized the great importance of pragmatics in language teaching and the urgent necessity to build learners' pragmatic competence.

According to G. Kasper [9], pragmatics means investigation of how speakers use a language and how their use affects their interlocutors. In D. Crystal's opinion "Pragmatics studies the factors that govern our choice of language in social interaction and the effects of our choice on others" [6, p.120-121]. The Common European Framework views the pragmatic competence as a constituent of the communicative competence alongside the linguistic and sociolinguistic ones. These definitions prompt that traditional approaches to teaching languages failed to allow teachers to instruct learners how to use language.

Pragmatic competence is thought to comprise different abilities in the use of language in context. Brock and Nagasaka point out that these abilities "include the speaker's ability to use language for different purposes (such as greeting, requesting, informing, demanding and so on), the speaker's ability to adapt or change language according to the needs or expectations of the listener or situation, and the speaker's ability to follow accepted rules, the maxims...for conversation and narrative" [5, p.19].

Thus the tradition of teaching foreign languages has made an important step forward. The change was made by specialists in pragmatics who revealed the drawbacks in the domain and highlighted the tasks in the modern theory of teaching foreign languages. In order to get learners communicate successfully in a foreign language, their pragmatic competence must be well developed and this is stressful for teachers as they have to accomplish very serious tasks. They realize

that it is their responsibility to get students ready for successful communication. In spite of this, most of their attention is continuously directed to developing students' linguistic competence and very often they consider grammatical errors more serious than pragmatic ones. It is worth mentioning here that native speakers of English are usually very tolerant to foreigners' grammatical mistakes, while pragmatic errors that lead to communication failures are considered more upsetting [13, p.97].

To be able to succeed our teachers should themselves get some training in how to develop their students' pragmatic competence. Given the situation in Moldova, this really is very difficult as pragmatics does not yet play a central role in teacher training and the number of teachers who have ever stayed in an English speaking country is astonishingly small. Eva Ogiermann writes that "it is necessary to extend the amount of time that future teachers of English are required to spend in the target culture" [12, p. 12]. This means that teachers and students in Germany do spend some time there. Unfortunately, we have to admit that neither our students who are being trained to become teachers of English, nor working teachers have any possibility to do this. Thus, in order to succeed, teachers should get some instruction by self-learning using whatever is possible to use. Here we should also consider the fact that our National Curriculum does not pay enough attention to pragmatic issues and this leaves teachers to work on it independently.

What often happens at the English lessons in many of our schools and in universities is transmission of information, learning to get informed, literal interpretation and translation and transferring pragmatic features from learners' native language to the foreign one and often the main criterion of assessing students' knowledge is still grammar. Considering the conditions under which foreign languages are taught and learned, we understand that the textbook should play an immense role in providing pragmatic information and thus help teachers do their job. This, however, does not often happen. As Bardovi-Harlig [1, p.24] points out, most course books "fail short of providing realistic input for learners". Heidi Vellinga has analysed eight textbooks written by native speakers including such world famous textbooks as Headway Upper Intermediate, Oxford, Interchange 2, Cambridge, Passages 1, Cambridge and Voyages 2, Prentice Hall Regents. As a result, she points out that "the amount of pragmatic information is small across all texts" and even when it is

included, it is frequently limited in the range of options for expression presented to students”. That is why she concludes that “learning pragmatics from textbooks is highly unlikely” [14, p.13].

This does not mean, however, that there is nothing left for us to improve the situation by creating the necessary conditions for the development of learners’ pragmatic competence. There is no doubt that the textbook remains a very important tool and together with various additional materials the teacher brings to the classroom and the techniques he or she uses, it may contribute to developing pragmatic competence. As no investigation based on textbooks from the point of view of pragmatic competence has ever been done in Moldova, I decided to analyse some of them and see how much implicit and explicit pragmatic information they contain. If we look more carefully through the English textbooks that are being used in Moldovan schools, we can easily see that they do not provide enough pragmatic input. My intention was to state how much information on pragmatics, if any, is contained in our school textbooks, how speech acts are treated and how many of them are found in the textbooks and how they teach politeness, this very important aspect of linguistic pragmatics. As this is the first attempt to analyse English textbooks from the point of view of the quantity and quality of pragmatic information contained in them, I selected those which are being used in our schools throughout the country in the II – VI forms. They are *Magic English*, by Iu.Ignatiuc, L.Aladina, L.Foca, D.Puiu, A.Muntean, for forms II, III and IV, published by Arc Publishing House and *English for You*, by the same authors, for forms V and VI, published by Prut Publishing House. The choice of these textbooks is justified by the necessity to start developing pragmatic competence at the earliest levels. I aimed at analyzing the pragmatic information that is found in the textbooks for developing pupils’ pragmatic competence. Pragmatic information means the information about culture, politeness, speech acts and metalanguage used to formulate the tasks and explain the grammatical and usage points [14, p.4]. Attention was also paid to the use of personal pronouns in the texts of tasks as this is an important but unexplored area of textbook analysis [3, p.199] though these pronouns produce a positive effect on learners of English making the tasks sound friendly.

From the first sight it is easy to notice that most tasks in all five English textbooks are formulated using imperative sentences. However, there are numerous cases when tasks include pronominal

reference, for example: Draw a picture of your room (ME, II, p.71), Say what you and your friends are doing now (ME II, p.75), Read and say where you were in your dream (ME III, p.75), How many of these words do you recognize? (ME IV, p. 64), Make a list of things you share with your friends (ME IV, p.35) Say if you would like to have such a friend (E for You V, p.8), Check if you can remember what Tim tells you (E for You, VI, p. 85), Go to a local post office and learn what you can do there (E for you, VI, p. 87). Such tasks sound friendlier. The use of pronouns in titles of lessons is advantageous too as pupils feel involved from the very beginning of the lesson, for example: Do You Play Tennis? (ME II, p.62), What Do You Do on Sunday? (ME II, p.66), I Am Playing (ME II, p. 74), I Am Your Friend (ME III, p.8), What's Your Address? (ME III, p.38), We Wish You a Merry Christmas (ME III, p.50), All about Me (ME III, p. 52), My School (ME IV, p.20), What's Your Favourite Subject? (ME IV, p.24), What Do They Do? (ME IV, p.26), Are You Ready for Fun (ME IV, p.92), Books in My Life (E for You V, p.60), I Have Done It (E for You V, p.78), At My Grandparents' (E for You VI, p. 16), Shall We Go Shopping? (E for You VI, p.70). Examples of this type are numerous, especially in the text books for the primary school. Due to the presence of such task formulations, pupils implicitly learn that directives are not expressed only by imperative sentences. This is important because the use of only imperative sentences in task formulations may convey "...undesired illocutionary force through unintentional language choices" [7, p.40]. There may be a greater variety of task formulations in the analysed textbooks. For example, using modal verbs would make the tasks sound more softly and politely and the authors of the textbooks under study have used, though not very often, modals in task formulations: Granny cannot find her glasses to read Angela's letter. Can you help her read it? (ME III, p.81), Look at the picture, name the things and say where you can buy them (ME IV, p.64), In groups discuss what people should do to help nature survive. The following words and word combinations may help you. (E for You VI, p.29). A lot of other tasks could be reformulated using modal verbs. Thus the task to exercise 8, p.91 in Magic English IV Choose the right word and copy the sentences could be replaced by If you can choose the right word you will make correct sentences; instead of Say where the children are and what they are doing in Magic English III, p.90, we could say Can you guess where the children are and what they are doing there? In the same textbook

at p. 97, the task Correct the mistakes could be replaced by Can you correct the mistakes? How many words can you find? would undoubtedly sound better than Find the words in Magic English II, p.97. To soften the tasks to exercises and to avoid making them sound like orders or commands, the word please could be used too, though this is not usual. Formulating lesson and text titles and tasks in textbooks is a very serious question, too and it deserves a separate investigation from the point of view of pragmatic consequences.

During the analysis of textbooks, attention was also paid to what information about socio-cultural rules they contain as this kind of information contributes to developing pragmatic competence by teaching pupils important things about correct use of language. The analysis shows that the textbooks provide some information of this kind, but this is limited and there is no focus on the importance of culture for correct use of language. This is partly because the National Curriculum ignores the role of culture in teaching and learning foreign languages. In *Magic English II* and *III* this information is represented by rhymes, songs and poems. In *Magic English IV* the rubric *Do you know that...* offers more information about Great Britain and its people. There are also several activities that teach pupils how to use English: *Read the invitation and answer the questions, Draw and write an invitation, Read Val's letter and...* In *English for You V* and *VI*, the rubric *Do you know that...* appears very seldom, three times in form V and four times in form VI. Teachers are expected to decide how to teach this material so as to make it possible to improve pupils' ability to use English. This, however, does not happen. Teachers admit that usually they simply read and translate the texts, but often omit them, depriving the pupils of the possibility to learn something new about English.

What follows is an analysis of the speech acts that the analysed English textbooks contain. Though the textbooks are centered on developing linguistic competence, various speech acts are found in all of them. We cannot, however, speak about a systemic presentation of speech acts in the textbooks. *Magic English II* pays more attention to teaching speech acts. Thus already in Lesson I of the introductory part, the characters greet each other, introduce themselves and say Goodbye using various strategies. They do it using dialogues which constitute an important way of including pragmatic information. These speech acts cover the material of the first five lessons, but they are repeatedly practiced later. They are followed by some imperative directives

(Listen and do. Read and write) which do not make it clear whether they express orders or requests, but this seems to be right at this level when the formulas are used for the first time. Similar directives are found in other lessons too. The use of please would make it clear that the imperative sentence is a request. Other forms could be used too, for example: *Will you...? Can/Could you...?* This will teach pupils from the very beginning that they may choose one variant out of more. Later they will learn that these variants are not always interchangeable. In other three lessons (p. 58, 73, 87), pupils learn how to apologize and how to respond to an apology.

Magic English II teaches greetings, making introductions, leave taking, orders, requests and responses to them and apologies and responses. While the first three speech acts are repeatedly used throughout the textbook, the others are sporadically used and not regularly repeated. Pupils continue to practise greetings, making introductions and leave taking with *Magic English III*. Besides they learn how to make suggestions and refuse them with this textbook. Thus in exercise 5, p.21, pupils are asked to play shopping, asking for things, offering them and thanking. In exercise 1, p. 26, there is a similar dialogue between a grandmother and her grandson in which pupils learn how to make offers (Tea, grandma? Cheese, Tim?), ask for things and give them (Pass me the sugar, please. Here you are.), refuse them (No, thank you, I'll have some biscuits.) and thank each other. In exercise 6, p.45, pupils learn to make suggestions using Let's... and how to refuse them offering an explanation:

-*Let's go out and ski.*

-*Sorry, I can't. I don't have skis.*

The dialogue on p. 60 teaches pupils how to make congratulations and respond to them. Exercise 5, p.93 allows pupils to practise offers using will: *It's cold. I will close the window; Go and have a rest. I will wash the dishes.* The textbook also teaches pupils how to disagree though they have not learnt how to agree to people yet. The textbook only occasionally provides models when introducing speech acts. Pupils are shown how to express disagreement only once in *Magic English III*, in exercise 6, p. 93: A. *Dan will go to Chişinău.*

B. *I'm afraid you are wrong. He will go to the country.*

In this exercise, pupils are expected to provide negative sentences in the simple future. *You are wrong* and *It's wrong* are usually used to teach pupils form negative sentences. They are, however, considered inappropriate and rude. Eva Ogiermann thinks that this formula

creates “the impression that it is an appropriate way of expressing disagreement in English” [12, p.5]. The use of *I’m afraid* in the example in the textbook helps the speaker sound more polite when disagreeing. There are no examples with *That’s wrong* which is good because, though such exercises help pupils distinguish true and false statements (there are numerous exercises of this type), it is not desirable to repeat them for the reason mentioned above. In an earlier exercise on p.73, pupils are asked to disagree with Ruddy Fox, but the given example does not sound very polite even though *You are wrong* is not used. An introductory sentence (I think, I suppose, I’m afraid) would make it sound better. In *Magic English IV*, pupils continue to practice requests using ‘could’. In exercise 8, p.9, pupils are told explicitly to make suggestions using ‘Shall...’. There are various exercises on the speech acts of greetings and responses, invitations and accepting or refusing them, congratulations and responses and thanking.

While *Magic English II, III* and *IV* contain some important information that allows pupils to learn how to perform different speech acts, *English for You V* and *VI* make use of more narrative texts and the number of dialogues is decreasing. This is due to pupils’ richer vocabulary and better grammar knowledge. Pragmatic information in textbooks often decreases at higher levels when the learners are more proficient. *English for You V* and *VI* are based on various topics. The Word Bank in each lesson and Do you know these words? in the Reading Together section are limited only to the new words. They could, however, be more effective if they contained different formulae expressing speech acts and this would greatly contribute to successful communication in the classroom and to the development of pragmatic competence. In *English for You V* and *VI*, pupils continue to practise greetings and responses to them, agreeing and disagreeing, requests and responses, suggestions, apologies, thanks and offers. They also learn to give advice. It is worth mentioning that in the last two textbooks more attention is paid to teaching more complicated grammar and vocabulary. The few speech acts that the textbooks contain are not used systematically and frequently enough although “pragmatic knowledge needs to be built up incrementally and continuously” [12, p.9].

To conclude it is necessary to point out that the analysis of the five English textbooks used in the Republic of Moldova in the primary school and in the first two years of the gymnasium clearly shows that

they contain a certain amount of implicit and explicit pragmatic information. However, this information is not systematically presented and frequently practised. The textbooks teach twenty-one speech acts, but not all of them frequently enough. Such important speech acts as compliments, regrets, and complaints have not even been mentioned. This might be explained by the fact that at the age of 8-12, children seldom make compliments. As for complaints, according to latest empirical studies, they are very seldom used in conversation. Regrets, however, have to be taught at this level as pupils should know how to express them sounding very polite. On the whole, the analysis shows that it is necessary to improve the textbooks from the point of view of the pragmatic aspect and thus raise their role in the development of pragmatic competence.

It is desirable that textbooks help pupils become aware of the pragmatic differences between the native and the foreign languages. This is necessary because often pupils possess good vocabulary and knowledge of important grammatical structures but are not able to use them and they express speech acts using translations from their native language which means they transfer pragmatic features from the mother tongue to English.

It seems clear enough that the quality of the textbooks can be improved only if: a) the National Curriculum emphasizes the importance of the pragmatic aspect in teaching foreign languages; b) the authors of textbooks focus not only on developing pupils' linguistic competence but also the pragmatic one; c) the teachers are well aware of what pragmatics is and of how the pragmatic competence should be developed.

Teachers' responsibility is great as they should become competent in the domain in order to succeed in teaching their pupils how to use English in practice. This requires a lot of independent work that is not a problem nowadays when we have numerous internet resource materials at our disposal. Universities could help a lot by organizing special courses for teachers.

References:

1. Bardovi-Harlig, K. Evaluating the empirical evidence: Grounds for Instruction in Pragmatics?// K.Rose & G.Kasper (Eds.), Pragmatics in Language Teaching. New York: Cambridge University Press, 2001. – P. 13-32

2. Bardovi-Harlig, K. et al.// Developing Pragmatic Awareness: Closing the Conversation.// *ELT Journal*. -1991. 45 (1) – P.4-15
3. Berry, R. “You-ser” Friendly Metalanguage: What Effect Does It Have on Learners of English?// *International Review of Applied Linguistics in Language Teaching*. – 2000. 38- P.195-211
4. Blum-Kulka, S., House, J., & Kasper, G. (Eds.). *Cross-cultural Pragmatics: Requests and Apologies*. Norwood, NJ: Ablex, 1989. – P.196-212
5. Brock, M., Nagasaka, J., Teaching Pragmatics in the EFL Classroom? SURE You Can! // *TESL Reporter*. – 2005. –num.1, vol.38 – P.17-26
6. Crystal, D. *The Cambridge Encyclopedia of Language*. New York: Cambridge University Press, 1987 – P. 120-121
7. Grant, L., Starks, D. Screening appropriate teaching materials: Closing from textbooks and television soap operas. // *International Review of Applied Linguistics in Language Teaching*. - 2001. – vol.39 – P. 39-50
8. Kasper, G., Blum-Kulka, S. Interlanguage pragmatics: An introduction. // Kasper, G., Blum-Kulka, S. (eds): *Interlanguage Pragmatics*. Oxford: OUP. -1993. – P. 3–17.
9. Kasper, G. Can pragmatic competence be taught? Second Language Teaching and Curriculum Center. University of Hawaii. – 1997. Available URL: <http://www.nflrc.hawaii.edu/NetWorks/NW06/> [accessed 21March 2018]
10. Kasper, G., Rose, K. R. *Pragmatic Development in a Second Language*. Malden, MA/Oxford: Blackwell, 2002 – 212 p.
11. Leech, G. *Principles of Pragmatics*. New York: Longman, 1983. – 250 p.
12. Ogiermann, E. Teaching Politeness with Green Line New. 2015. Available URL: https://www.researchgate.net/.../282809616_ [accessed 15 April 2018] – 16 p.
13. Thomas, J. Cross-cultural pragmatic failure. // *Applied Linguistics*.-1983. – num.2, vol.4 – P.91- 111
14. Vellenga, H. Learning pragmatics from ESL & EFL textbooks: How likely?// *The Electronic Journal for English as a Second Language*. – 2004. – num.2, vol. 8 -15 p.